

Enhancing EV Charging Management with Dynamic Pricing and Edge Intelligence

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Abstract—This paper proposes a comprehensive solution for smart charging of electric vehicles (EVs) based on the Internet of Things (IoT) and Edge Intelligence (EI) technologies. It integrates a dynamic pricing algorithm executed by software agents and EI-based technologies for detecting parked cars at charging stations and load balancing with a Charge Point Management System (CPMS). The dynamic pricing algorithm continuously adjusts the charging costs for groups of stations based on real-time electricity demand and station availability, incentivizing off-peak charging. Furthermore, the edge solution effectively identifies the occupancy of a parking lot and simultaneously checks the charging period, preventing misuse of charging spots to maximize their availability for EVs. It represents a large-scale distributed IoT solution that relies on Modbus RTU for smart power meters, Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) to interconnect EV chargers, and Kafka messaging to seamlessly integrate parking lot occupancy and pricing information into a scalable solution. By improving the utilization of the charging stations through dynamic pricing and EI, this solution aims to reduce the load on the electricity grid to support a reliable e-mobility ecosystem.

Index Terms—Smart Charging, Power Meter, Open Charge Point Protocol, Computer Vision, Edge Computing, Kafka Messaging

I. INTRODUCTION

The transportation sector is undergoing a significant transformation with the widespread adoption of electric vehicles (EVs). While this shift offers environmental benefits with a lower carbon footprint and reduced air pollution for cities, it also presents a growing challenge for electricity grids due to unbalanced electricity demand and supply. This imbalance is exacerbated by the inefficient use of charging stations due to improper parking practices and fixed pricing models. A large network of EV charging stations, acting as the primary energy consumers, can disrupt grid stability and sustainability, particularly during peak demand periods [1]. However, if managed smartly, it presents an opportunity to enhance grid stability and

Fig. 1. Day ahead market price and charging electricity price in Croatia on 20th February 2025

support the integration of green energy sources. If the grid can control demand or at least make it more predictable, the EV charging infrastructure, together with vehicles, can be viewed as a massive energy storage system on wheels. This issue also raises the question of energy market liberalization. For example, Fig. 1 compares a Day-Ahead Market price [2] with the AC charging service price based on the traditional two-tariff model for public chargers by Croatian national power company HEP - ELEN [3]. A clear disbalance between the two prices can be observed.

To address this challenge, a number of technologies are emerging to integrate EVs and intelligent charging stations via specific communication protocols into a large Smart Grid framework [4]. Smart charging stations utilize microcontrollers, processors, and network connectivity to communicate with a central control system. Smart chargers are the first group of devices considered as edge nodes. They collect data from various sensors and meters, process this data in real time, and

execute control algorithms to optimize charging operations [5]. This communication is facilitated by the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) which supports real-time monitoring and control of charging parameters, including power output¹. By dynamically adjusting the charging power based on grid conditions, smart charging can significantly improve grid stability and efficiency.

This paper presents the design and implementation of an advanced smart charging solution that improves the utilization of electricity network resources while maximizing the utilization of charging stations. The solution supports dynamic pricing models for charging which depend on various parameters, such as time of day, station location, etc. Beyond dynamic station management, the proposed system incorporates an edge-driven vehicle detection system for rapid identification and response to unauthorized parking at charging stations. The solution leverages edge computing and artificial intelligence (AI) for efficient management of parking lots at charging stations, specifically employing vehicle recognition to identify and apply control measures to non-charging vehicles to improve charger availability and usage.

The architecture of the proposed smart charging solution is based on microservices and employs Apache Kafka², a distributed event streaming platform, to facilitate the exchange of data across microservices for vehicle detection deployed on edge devices and dynamic pricing services integrated with a wide network of charging stations. Kafka's main role is to enable near real-time distribution of information related to charging status, parking lot availability and status, as well as instructions on pricing strategies. Kafka is used for scalability to ensure that the infrastructure can handle a growing number of charging stations and increasing data volumes while maintaining the required a near-real-time performance. Dynamic pricing allows users to save money on charging costs in line with the analyses have demonstrating the economic attractiveness of smart charging in different electricity markets, with potential financial benefits ranging from 106 €/year to 1008 €/year per EV [6].

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents related work on dynamic pricing strategies, smart charging, and EI for EV infrastructure. Section III describes the proposed solution, outlining the system architecture, key components, and their interactions. Section IV details the implementation of dynamic load balancing, pricing optimization, and parking management. It discusses the demonstrator setup and initial evaluation results, highlighting system performance and limitations. Concluding remarks and directions for future research are provided in Section V.

¹OCPP is a manufacturer-agnostic and open protocol for communication between charging stations and the central control system, and supports cross-vendor interoperability. For more information: OCPP 1.6 specification, https://groups.oasis-open.org/higherlogic/ws/public/document?document_id=58944

²Apache Kafka, <https://kafka.apache.org/>

II. RELATED WORK

The challenge of efficiently managing parking spaces at charging stations while implementing dynamic pricing strategies to influence charging behavior is still relatively unexplored. Relevant works addressing either efficient management of charging stations or dynamic pricing models, which represent the starting point for the solution, are reviewed hereafter.

[7] explores a deployment of smart charging infrastructure at parking lots of a private company and highlighting the importance of workplace charging for widespread EV adoption in densely populated areas. [8] introduces a dynamic and responsive charging management solutions which includes a dynamic pricing strategy for EV charging stations aimed at avoiding congestion and enhancing revenue. Another paper [9] presents a coordinated dynamic pricing model for EV charging stations which aims to maximize utility and revenue by encouraging EV owners to charge during off-peak hours or when renewable energy is readily available. The role of standards in the development of charging infrastructure is crucial as it ensures interoperability across different systems [1]. Thus, it impacts both the deployment of dynamic pricing models and smart charging solutions. [10] highlights the importance of AI in optimizing EV charging and discharging schedules, as well as in implementing dynamic pricing models. AI techniques, particularly neural networks and reinforcement learning, are identified as superior to conventional optimization methods for forecasting EV charging demand and scheduling. This is attributed to AI's ability to model complex, non-linear relationships and adapt to evolving system dynamics, offering a more nuanced understanding and management of charging demands. [5] indicates that an edge-based platform demonstrates robustness in adapting to fluctuating demand and varied station capacities. These results suggest that implementing edge computing in existing charging infrastructure can offer substantial benefits in terms of operational efficiency and energy management.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The proposed smart charging solution adopts a microservices architecture enhanced with edge computing and IoT devices to ensure scalability and flexibility. The system is composed of an OCPP Server, CPMS API with an SQL database and frontend application, a dynamic pricing software agent, Kafka as a central messaging broker, charging points, a power meter, and an Nvidia Jetson Nano for parking management, as shown in Fig. 2.

The OCPP Server enables communication with charging points via WebSocket-based OCPP, while the CPMS API handles business logic, user interactions, and integration with dynamic pricing and parking management. The pricing agent adjusts charging costs based on real-time charger usage and day-ahead electricity prices, retrieving market data via REST API and publishing updates via Kafka. Kafka ensures real-time event-driven communication between system components. The power meter, connected via Modbus RTU, enables dynamic load balancing, while Nvidia Jetson Nano processes parking

Fig. 2. Architecture of the proposed charging management solution

lot images, detecting unauthorized use and publishing results via Kafka.

Each component is explained in more detail in the following sections.

A. Charging Core - CPMS and OCPP server

The CPMS API is the central hub for business logic. It manages the interactions between the system's components and the relational database, overseeing CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations on data entities. This API is responsible for serving the web application, providing a user interface for system interaction, and handling administrative tasks. It processes requests related to charger management, user authentication, and transaction processing, ensuring efficient operation of the charging stations. It uses SQL relational database.

The OCPP WebSocket Server stands as a cornerstone within the system's architecture, playing a critical role in enabling real-time interactions between the central management system and each electric vehicle (EV) charger. This server is specifically designed to implement the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP), which is a standardized protocol for communication between EV charging stations and a central management system. The adoption of OCPP ensures interoperability across different charger manufacturers and models, facilitating a wide-reaching and flexible charging infrastructure.

The OCPP server establishes and maintains persistent WebSocket connections (using `ws://` channels) with EV chargers,

enabling bidirectional, real-time communication. This capability is essential for transmitting commands, receiving status updates, and ensuring that chargers operate in accordance with the central system's directives. It is designed as a separate component from the CPMS application to ensure seamless scalability as the number of chargers and connections increases, without requiring the scaling of other parts of the solution.

Operational data, including status updates and metrics from sensors within the chargers, are continuously collected by the server. This data provides valuable insights into charger performance, usage patterns, and potential issues, enabling proactive maintenance and system optimization.

B. Smart Power Meter for Dynamic Load Balancing

Load management is a technique for controlling charging power at a local level to prevent exceeding the maximum capacity of the electrical grid connection. OCPP supports this functionality via the ChargingProfile feature in OCPP 1.6, enabling remote control and optimization of charging power.

Energy demand at a location varies based on factors like time of day, weekdays vs. weekends, and weather conditions. A dynamic load management system distributes available capacity among charging points, considering real-time site loads (e.g., building consumption). If building consumption increases, the available charging power is reduced to stay within the grid connection limit. Implementing this requires

additional measurement devices to track real-time power usage and adjust charging accordingly.

Three-phase smart energy meters, such as the EMU Professional II, provide precise measurement and monitoring of electricity consumption. These meters are essential for energy management across residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. They support multiple communication interfaces, including M-Bus, Modbus TCP/IP, Modbus RTU, and LoRa, ensuring seamless integration into energy management systems. Modbus RTU - RS-485 is the used interface. In this scenario, one charger of the multiple-charger installation is Modbus Primary and acts as an interface to inform the cloud server about the smart meter status. Load management strategy is executed from the CPMS and OCPP Server.

An example of dynamic load balancing in a scenario with three chargers charging simultaneously, along with external measured active power (EV charging and non-EV charging demand), under a grid limit, is shown in Fig. 3.

At time t_1 , charger 1 initiates the charging process, receiving the available current, which at this moment corresponds to its maximum input current of 32 A. Until t_2 , it charges at a constant current since the total external meter reading remains within the optimal range, bounded by the lower and upper limits.

If the external meter reading falls below the lower limit and chargers are not already operating at their maximum currents, their currents will be increased. Conversely, if the external meter reading exceeds the upper limit but remains below the alarm threshold, the charger currents will be reduced. In cases where the external meter reading surpasses the alarm limit, charger currents will be decreased more strictly.

At t_2 , charger 2 begins charging. The available current is now divided between the two chargers, reducing each to 16A. However, due to additional demand, the external power meter reading reaches the upper limit, prompting a decrease in both chargers' currents at t_3 .

At t_4 , charger 3 starts charging. Subsequently, at t_5 , the external power meter reading drops below the lower limit, causing an increase in charging currents across all chargers.

Fig. 3. Diagram of multiple EV chargers operating with DLM (Dynamic Load Management)

This pattern continues, dynamically adjusting currents based on external meter readings and additional charger activations or deactivations. The process proceeds until t_{11} , when no active charging sessions remain, and the external power meter reflects only the current demand unrelated to EV charging.

C. Software Agent for Intelligent Price Optimization

The software agent processes charging times and occupancy rates, using predictive analytics to dynamically adjust charging prices. By analyzing Kafka stream data and external electricity market rates, the agent optimizes pricing to encourage off-peak charging and improve charger utilization, enhancing grid stability and efficiency.

Implemented as a separate Java service with Apache Maven, the agent initializes by simulating seven days of charger occupancy data. Based on this and API-fetched electricity prices, it calculates the initial charging prices (€/kWh) and sends hourly updates via Kafka producers to pricelist-category topics. The central system, subscribed to these topics, applies the prices at charging stations.

Kafka subscribers for each charger category listen to occupancy-category topics, receiving messages when charging sessions end. These messages contain charging duration and session timestamps, which subscribers format and store in a structured map categorized by the hour of the day. This ensures that occupancy trends are analyzed per hour, rather than as a daily total.

A Java Timer schedules hourly price updates, triggering tasks at the start of each hour. The agent fetches day-ahead market electricity prices at 21 for the next day. Then it calculates optimal prices and stores them in memory. These base prices are then multiplied by the charger utilization coefficient across different categories, determining the markup for the EV charging service.

The agent determines optimal prices by analyzing past eight-day charger occupancy data, categorized by hour. It adjusts a coefficient (range: 3-7, default: 5) based on changes in hourly charging duration trends. If a specific hour sees increased charging duration compared to its historical average, the coefficient for that hour rises; otherwise, it decreases. To prevent values from staying at limits, correction mechanisms shift coefficients across charger categories.

Hourly Kafka messages transmit price updates after all calculations. The optimization algorithm leverages hourly historical usage patterns and real-time adjustments to encourage off-peak charging and enhance grid stability.

D. Parking Management with EI

Leveraging the edge computing capabilities of Nvidia Jetson Nano devices, this microservice specializes in real-time vehicle detection at charging stations. It monitors parking spots to identify unauthorized vehicle occupancy and communicates this information to the Charge Point Management System (CPMS) via Kafka, ensuring optimal utilization of charging infrastructure. This integration of computer vision and edge computing differentiates between vehicles actively charging

and those merely occupying space. By processing data locally and transmitting only metadata to the cloud, the system preserves privacy and significantly reduces the data traffic transitted to the cloud.

The system employs an Nvidia Jetson Nano device with a surveillance camera to monitor parking lots in real-time. Using a deep neural network-based object detection model, it accurately identifies parked vehicles and distinguishes them from irrelevant objects. The solution consists of the following:

- **Object Detection:** YOLO (You Only Look Once) model is used for real-time detection and classification of vehicles [11].
- **Computer Vision Server:** Deepstack, an open-source multi-platform server, provides various pre-trained models, including YOLO-based vehicle detection [12].
- **Data Communication:** Kafka serves as the messaging broker to ensure real-time exchange of events between edge devices and the central CPMS.

The YOLOv5 model is used to detect parked vehicles within camera frames. Unlike traditional motion and presence detection sensors, object detection, a primary application of YOLOv5, entails the extraction of salient features from input images. [13] YOLO is a unified object detection framework, training on full images with a loss function optimized for detection performance. It is particularly suitable for low-power edge devices due to its speed and efficiency [11].

To safeguard user privacy, all image processing is conducted on edge devices, ensuring that sensitive visual data remains stored locally. The system transmits only the metadata, including 1) station identifier, 2) timestamp and 3) parking state (occupied or empty). This approach minimizes network traffic while enabling real-time monitoring and management of parking spaces.

IV. DEMONSTRATOR SETUP AND INITIAL EVALUATION

The solution has been implemented and tested in a lab environment with simulated charging sessions, but not yet deployed in production.

A. Deployment and Messaging

For deployment, a lightweight Kubernetes cluster managed by k3s runs on a virtual machine with 4 CPUs, 4GB RAM, and 40GB storage. The k3s cluster, deployed using k3d, consists of three server nodes and five agent nodes, balancing workloads across application instances. Load balancers manage client traffic and ensure efficient distribution of containerized applications. The software agent integrates with Kafka, producing data for various consumers without additional processing overhead. This architecture provides scalability, resilience, and efficient resource utilization while ensuring seamless communication and deployment.

The system employs Apache Kafka for real-time messaging between key components, including the software agent, Nvidia Jetson Nano devices, and the central charging management system as shown in Fig. 4. A Kafka cluster with three brokers ensures message replication and fault tolerance, with

Fig. 4. Kafka topics and their producers and consumers

topics categorized by charger occupancy, pricing, and vehicle detection. JSON-formatted messages allow seamless data exchange, such as price updates and charging session details. The system’s scalability is achieved by dynamically adding topics for new geographic regions or charger categories.

B. Dynamic Pricing Setup and Evaluation

The pricing software agent runs in a Dockerized k3s cluster on a faculty server. Day-ahead market prices are fetched via a REST API daily and pushed hourly to CPMS via Kafka. Pricing adjustments are based on simulated charging session data, limiting real-world validation. The system successfully fetched prices, computed adjustments, and updated CPMS in real-time. However, mock data prevented the assessment of actual demand shifts. Future work should incorporate real-world session data.

C. Load Management Setup and Evaluation

A Modbus RTU smart meter (EMU Professional II) was deployed with an ABB Terra AC charger as the primary node. Two additional simulated EV chargers were used for testing. Power limits were set to 90A (grid limit), 88A (upper limit), and 75A (lower limit). Since the simulators were virtual, their power draw was summed with physical meter readings. The system dynamically adjusted charging power per availability from a cloud. Demand exceeding 88A triggered load reduction, while values below 75A allowed increased allocation. The absence of multiple installed real chargers limited full validation.

D. Parking Management Setup and Evaluation

Deepstack’s pre-trained YOLO models enable vehicle and license plate detection. Although initially trained on Norwegian license plates, the model exhibits cross-country compatibility [14]. Optical character recognition (OCR) using Tesseract was considered for extracting license plate text but was discarded due to hardware limitations. The computational requirements of OCR exceeded the capabilities of Nvidia Jetson Nano, making real-time conversion impractical. Performance testing highlights the need for hardware upgrades to enable real-time license plate recognition. Current computational limitations affect system responsiveness, but future iterations can leverage enhanced hardware such as Nvidia Jetson Orin, offering increased computational power

and efficiency. Integrating such advancements will optimize the performance of the system, ensuring seamless real-time monitoring and improved parking space management.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The increasing adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) necessitates intelligent charging solutions to address challenges such as grid stability, inefficient charging station utilization, and improper parking management. This paper presents a scalable smart charging system that enhances a traditional Charge Point Management System (CPMS) by integrating dynamic load balancing, dynamic pricing, and intelligent EV parking management. Built on a containerized microservices architecture with Apache Kafka for real-time data streaming, the proposed solution ensures efficient communication and operational scalability.

1) Dynamic Load Balancing: Smart power meters utilizing Modbus RTU-based communication enable real-time load monitoring and dynamic power allocation. By continuously adjusting charging power distribution based on site-wide energy demand, the system prevents grid overload while maximizing charger availability. This ensures optimal energy distribution and cost efficiency without requiring major grid infrastructure upgrades.

2) Dynamic Pricing Optimization: A software agent analyzes real-time charger occupancy, historical usage patterns, and day-ahead market electricity prices to determine optimal charging rates. Leveraging Apache Kafka for real-time data streaming, the system dynamically adjusts pricing to incentivize off-peak charging, reducing peak demand stress on the grid. This approach enhances both economic viability for charging station operators and cost savings for users.

3) Intelligent EV Parking Management: Edge computing with Nvidia Jetson Nano enables real-time vehicle recognition, detecting unauthorized parking at charging spots. A deep learning-based object detection model identifies non-charging vehicles, transmitting occupancy status to the CPMS via Kafka. This solution improves charger availability and ensures more efficient station utilization.

By integrating these three capabilities on top of an OCPP-based CPMS, the proposed solution significantly enhances the efficiency, availability, and scalability of EV charging networks.

Future research should focus on several key enhancements to further improve the proposed smart charging solution. A crucial aspect will be the integration of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, to minimize the carbon footprint of EV charging. The implementation of blockchain technology could also be explored to enhance transparency and security in transaction management within the charging ecosystem.

Advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning will be essential for refining demand forecasting, price optimization, and predictive maintenance, making the charging network even more efficient. Additionally, expanding the vehicle detection capabilities could enable license plate recognition

and more precise EV identification, further optimizing parking enforcement.

As the EV charging ecosystem evolves, developing and adhering to broader interoperability standards will be critical to ensuring seamless communication between different CPMS providers, charging stations, and grid operators. Finally, the deployment of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology presents an exciting opportunity, allowing EVs to act as mobile energy storage units and contribute to grid stability. These advancements will drive the evolution of smart charging infrastructure, supporting a more resilient, sustainable, and intelligent e-mobility ecosystem.

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